

Enhanced Power Performance of Highly Mesoporous Sol-Gel TiC Derived Carbons in Ionic Liquid and Non-Aqueous Electrolyte Based Capacitors

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The electrical double layer capacitors (EDLC) based on hierarchical micro-mesoporous sol-gel TiC derived carbon (SgTiC-CDC) electrodes and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate (EtMeImBF₄) and 1 M Et₃MeNBF₄ + acetonitrile (AN) as the electrolytes were tested to establish the electrochemical characteristics and region of ideal polarizability. The precursors for the micro-mesoporous carbon electrodes were synthesized via modified sol-gel synthesis process. Compared to traditional titanium carbide derived carbons, where precursor carbide is commercially available, the sol-gel TiC derived hierarchical carbon materials exhibit larger specific density functional theory (DFT) surface areas (up to 1700 m² g⁻¹) and a unique pore size distribution with more mesopores between 2 and 10 nm. The electrochemical properties of the EDLCs were investigated using the cyclic voltammetry, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, galvanostatic charge/discharge and constant power discharge methods. The EDLCs demonstrated nearly ideal capacitive behavior even at very high charging/discharging currents (10 A g⁻¹) and cell potential scan rates (500 mV s⁻¹). The EDLCs completed from SgTiC-CDC materials and EtMeImBF₄ and Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN show good energy efficiencies (varying from 93% to 95% at current 1 A g⁻¹) and coulombic efficiency values exceeded 99%. Thus, the EDLCs completed are very promising devices for extremely high power/energy density applications.

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There is an ever increasing demand for energy storage/generation devices that are environmentally friendly and that also can deliver high peak power and energy pulses for different electrical devices, like cars, buses, trucks, etc.¹⁻⁵ Thus, batteries, electrical double layer capacitors (EDLCs) and fuel-cells are energy storage and conversion devices that meet energy efficiency criteria.^{1-3,6-12} The commercialization of EDLCs has vastly increased due to their extremely high power delivery characteristics that fills the gap between the dielectric capacitors and traditional batteries.^{1-3,6-9} EDLCs have gained much attention because they have high specific capacitance, very long cycle life, very high power density and very low maintenance costs etc.^{1,13-24} One of the most used electrode material in EDLCs are different porous carbon materials.^{7,9,25-32} One limiting factor in achieving high energy and power density is the moderate working cell potential of the aqueous and some protic electrolytes (including protic ionic liquids) that are used for completing of EDLCs.^{2,13,33,34} So, using room temperature non-protic ionic liquids (RTIL) as EDLC electrolyte instead of aqueous electrolyte solutions, there is a good alternative for achieving higher energy and power densities because of RTIL high electrochemical stability within very wide cell potential region.^{2,14,21,35-39} To achieve excellent performance of EDLC it is important to optimize the characteristics of components like electrodes micro-mesoporosity, pore size distribution, thickness of the electrodes and conductivity and finite-length mass transfer rate discussed by R. de Levie^{40,41} as the distributed charge storage mechanism of electrolyte ions inside the micro-mesoporous electrode matrix. The relationship between the ion size and pore size has been discussed in many papers^{17,19,42-47} including the relationship of power density and energy density and dependence of mentioned parameters on the pore size distribution of EDLC materials.^{43,46-48} It was shown that for very microporous materials very low power densities have been achieved⁴⁷ and these materials are not applicable for high power density supercapacitors. It should be noted that there are very few experimental Ragone plots data measured for completed two electrode EDLCs.

1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate (EtMeImBF₄) ionic liquid was chosen due to the wide potential region of electrochemical stability, good conductivity (13.6 mS cm⁻¹) and moderate viscosity (38.2 mPa s),^{2,15-19} but also for better comparison of Ragone

plots data with EDLCs discussed in our previous studies.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ For comparison, the 1 M triethylmethylammoniumtetrafluoroborate solution in acetonitrile (Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN) electrolyte based EDLCs have been completed and studied. Compared to EtMeImBF₄ ionic liquid 1 M Et₃MeNBF₄ in AN has lower viscosity (0.41 mPa s) and higher electrical conductivity (50.2 mS cm⁻¹) and this electrolyte is also electrochemically stable within a very wide region of cell potentials. Carbon materials were synthesized from specially designed titanium carbide that had been synthesized via sol-gel method. A good agreement has been found between the work and for acetonitrile based EDLC published before,¹⁹ therefore, it can be concluded that the electrochemical data established after 24 months are very well reproducible.

Experimental

The experiments were carried out applying hierarchical micro- and mesoporous carbon materials obtained by chlorination of titanium carbide and titanium carbide/carbon nanotube (CNT) composites synthesized via sol-gel method under various synthesis conditions.¹⁹ CNTs have been added into raw electrode materials with main idea to increase the mesoporosity. N₂ and CO₂ sorption measurements have been conducted on ASAP 2020 (Micromeritics) and 3Flex (Micromeritics, USA) systems. In order to calculate the specific surface area (*S*_{DFT}), pore volume (*V*_{DFT}) and pore size distribution data, the 2D non-local density functional theory based on heterogeneous carbon surface model (2D-NLDFT HS) implemented in SAIEUS software (Micromeritics)⁴⁹ has been used. Raman data were recorded using Renishaw inVia Raman Microscope with laser wavelength 514 nm and the measurements were performed in a closed argon-filled cell with a glass window. For scanning electron microscopy studies, FEI Helios Nanolab 600 was used.

The EDLC electrodes were completed from mixture of carbon materials SgTiC-CDC (95 wt%) and 5% of PTFE binder (60% dispersion in H₂O). The electrode thickness after roll-pressing was 150 ± 5 μm. Pure Al layer (2 μm) was deposited onto one side of the electrode material by magnetron sputtering method.^{16-19,52-54}

For electrochemical measurements, the two-electrode standard Al test cell (HS Test Cell, Hohsen Corporation) with two identical electrodes (geometric area of about 2.0 cm²) was completed inside a glove box (Labmaster sp, MBraun; O₂ and H₂O concentrations lower than 0.1 ppm). For mechanical separation of electrodes, 25 μm thick

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Figure 1. Characteristic (a) Raman spectra and (b) X-ray diffraction data for synthesized sol-gel titanium carbide derived carbons (SgTiC-CDC) with and without additions of carbon nanotubes (CNT), noted in Figure.

TF4425 (Nippon Kodoshi) separator sheet was used. All electrochemical experiments were carried out at temperature $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Electrochemical characteristics of the EDLC cells, consisting of the synthesized carbon electrodes and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate (EtMeImBF₄, Sigma-Aldrich, for electrochemistry, $\geq 99.0\%$, HPLC) and 1M triethylmethylammoniumtetrafluoroborate (Et₃MeNBF₄, Stella Chemifa) + acetonitrile (AN, Sigma-Aldrich, H₂O < 20 ppm), have been studied by cyclic voltammetry, constant current charge/discharge and the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy methods using a SI1287 Solartron potentiostat and 1252A frequency response analyzer over ac frequency, (f), range from 1 mHz to 300 kHz at 5 mV modulation. Constant power tests were performed on a BT2000 testing system (Arbin Instruments, USA).

Results and Discussion

Raman spectroscopy and scanning electron microscopy analysis.—The Raman spectra show two main peaks for all the synthesized materials: 1348 cm⁻¹ (D-peak that originates from the edges of the ordered areas, i.e. from defects region in carbon structure), 1587 cm⁻¹ (G-peak that originates from the ordered graphite-like areas).^{47,55} The Raman spectra (Fig. 1a) for synthesized sol-gel derived carbon materials is characteristic of highly disordered micro- and mesoporous carbons.^{56,57} The addition of CNTs to the precursor carbide makes the resulting carbon material more disordered, evident of the intensity of the D-peak. For the carbon material with 2% CNT addition, well-developed 2D-peak can be seen, at 2700 cm⁻¹ (2D-peak, the second-order peak of D-band) which characterizes well-developed graphitization and stacking of sp² layers.^{47,55,58} X-ray diffraction (Fig. 1b) data show that there are some graphite areas in carbons (mainly at surface region) under study.¹⁹

The scanning electron microscopy images show that the precursor carbides synthesized via sol-gel method have wide particle size distribution (Fig. 2). Carbon material particle sizes without CNT addition (Fig. 2b) and with 1%–2% CNT addition (Figs. 2c and 2d) vary from 1 μm to 20 μm. Carbon nanotubes can be seen in the carbon sample with 1% CNT addition (Fig. 2c). Partially bundled carbon nanotubes can be seen on the surface of carbon particles in the sample with 2% CNT addition (Fig. 2d). Very big well crystallized particles can be seen in Figs. 2a–2c, with more or less exposed surface roughness. However, in Fig. 2b, very big particles with comparatively flat surface can be seen.

Scorption measurements.—The specific surface areas and pore size distributions have been obtained from combined N₂ and CO₂ adsorption isotherm using two-dimensional non-local density functional theory and heterogeneous surface model (2D-NLDFT-HS).⁴⁹ The adsorption/desorption isotherms in Fig. 3a show hysteresis loops, thus all the materials are micro-mesoporous, as shown in the derived pore size distribution data, given in Fig. 3b. All the synthesized materials have micropores below 2 nm and well-expressed amount of mesopores above 2 nm. The S_{DFT} data (Table I) show that the carbon material

without carbon nanotubes has the highest DFT specific surface area (1710 m² g⁻¹) and high degree of mesoporosity in addition to microporosity, suggesting that potentially this material may be good for EDLC applications.

Cyclic voltammetry data.—The cyclic voltammograms (CVs) for EDLC cells were measured within various electrode potential regions ΔE (up to 3.8 V) at potential scan rates (v) from 1 to 500 mV s⁻¹. Comparison of CV (or j , E) curves shows that the capacitance values for Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN non-aqueous electrolyte based EDLC is 15–20% lower than that for EtMeImBF₄ (ionic liquid) based EDLC. At potential scan rate $v \geq 500$ mV s⁻¹, less expressed deviation of C, E -curves from the shape for ideally polarizable electrode has been observed for Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN non-aqueous electrolyte system explained by the lower viscosity and higher conductivity of the electrolyte.

The integral capacitance^{6,46,59} values have been calculated over the cell potential range ΔE from 0 to 3.2 V using the integrated total charge density σ values obtained according to Eq. 1:

$$\sigma = \int_{\Delta E_1}^{\Delta E_2} i(\Delta E) dt \equiv \int_{\Delta E_1}^{\Delta E_2} i(\Delta E) \frac{d(\Delta E)}{v} \quad [1]$$

Eq. 1 can be used to calculate the capacitance values only within the region of moderate cell potential scan rates, if the values of current, i , are small, as only in these conditions the potential drop (IR-drop) is negligible. Only under these conditions the current response is essentially equal to that of a pure capacitor.^{3,6–8,17–19,52–54}

In a symmetrical two-electrode system the specific capacitance C_m (F g⁻¹) for one activated carbon electrode can be calculated from cell capacitance C as follows:

$$C_m = \frac{2C}{m}, \quad [2]$$

where m is the weight in g cm⁻² per one electrode, assuming that the positively and negatively charged electrodes have the same capacitance at fixed ΔE .

The specific capacitance ($C_{m,\text{CV}}$) (calculated from CV data) and surface charge density, σ , (presented in Fig. 4) demonstrate that there is a small dependence of $C_{m,\text{CV}}$ on the CNT addition in the SgTiC-CDC materials. All sol-gel TiC-CDC synthesized materials and EtMeImBF₄ based EDLCs demonstrate almost ideal capacitive behavior at cell potential scan rate $v \leq 500$ mV s⁻¹ and up to $\Delta E \leq 3.8$ V (Figs. 4e and 4f). The carbon material without CNT additions shows ideal capacitive behavior up to $\Delta E \leq 3.6$ V at cell potential scan rate $v \leq 100$ mV s⁻¹ (Fig. 4e). There is no significant potential drop arising from the porous carbon matrix and this is due to the additional mesoporosity (Fig. 3b), because the sol-gel synthesis method provides additional mesopores mainly in the region from 4 to 10 nm. Data in Figs. 4e and 4f show that for SgTiC-CDC two-electrode symmetrical cell no quick faradaic reactions occur up to 3.8 V in EtMeImBF₄ and 3.4 V in Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN.

Figure 2. SEM images of the synthesized (a) SgTiC/2%CNT; (b) SgTiC-CDC; (c) SgTiC/1%CNT-CDC and (d) SgTiC/2%CNT-CDC materials.

The calculated specific capacitance values are given in Table II. It is clearly visible that the capacitance values depend on the CNT additions in the SgTiC-CDC. The addition of CNT to TiC precursor material decreases the capacitance values of the EDLC that is completed using synthesized carbon materials (data given in Table II). This can be explained by the decrease of specific surface area (Tables I and II).^{17–19,52,53} The highest integrated capacitance value from cyclic voltammetry data, 122 F g^{-1} at $v = 10 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$, is obtained for the sample without CNT addition.

For more detailed analysis $C_{m,CV}$ vs ΔE curves have been integrated and the charge density σ vs ΔE plots received are given in Figs. 4d and 4f. Data in Figs. 4d and 4f show that very high σ values have been achieved for all EDLCs tested. Data in Fig. 4f show that EDLCs completed using TiC-CDC material (without CNT addition) σ vs ΔE plots are symmetrical within very wide potential region (up to 3.6 V) and only at higher potentials very weak influence of

faradaic processes can be seen. At $\Delta E = 3.2 \text{ V}$, τ values are only 10–12% lower for $\text{Et}_3\text{MeNBF}_4 + \text{AN}$ electrolyte based EDLC that for EtMeImBF_4 based EDLCs.

Constant current charge/discharge data.—The EDLCs were tested at constant current charge/discharge (CC/CD) regimes (at current densities from 0.05 to 10 A g^{-1}) at the cell potentials from 0 to 3.8 V for EtMeImBF_4 based EDLC (Fig. 5) and/or from 0 to 3.0 V for $\text{Et}_3\text{MeNBF}_4 + \text{AN}$ based EDLC.

The discharge and charge capacitances, C_{CC} , were calculated from the data of the third cycle. C_{CC} (F cm^{-2}) was obtained according to Eq. 3:^{52,60}

$$C_{CC} = \frac{\int_{\Delta E_1}^{\Delta E_2} j dt}{d(\Delta E)}, \quad [3]$$

Figure 3. (a) N_2 adsorption/desorption isotherms and (b) differential pore size distribution vs. pore width plots calculated by applying 2D-NLDFT-HS model to N_2 and CO_2 adsorption isotherms for materials noted in Figure.

Figure 4. Specific capacitance vs. cell potential curves calculated from CV curves at potential scan rates (a) $\nu = 10 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$, (b) $\nu = 100 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ (c) $\nu = 500 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ and (d) σ vs. ΔE plots for the EDLCs completed using SgTiC-CDC, SgTiC/1%CNT-CDC and SgTiC/2%CNT-CDC as electrodes (noted in Figure); (e) specific capacitance vs. cell potential curves calculated from CV curves at scan rate $\nu = 100 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ and (f) σ vs. ΔE plots for EDLC completed using SgTiC-CDC at different maximum cell potentials (noted in Figure).

Table I. Results of the sorption measurements for the materials under study calculated by applying 2D-NLDFT-HS model.

Electrode material	Carbide		Carbon	
	$S_{\text{DFT}} (\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1})$	$S_{\text{DFT}} (\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1})$	$V_{\text{micro}} (\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1})$	$V_{\text{tot}} (\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1})$
SgTiC-CDC	244	1710	0.45	2.85
SgTiC/1%CNT-CDC	152	1560	0.39	2.99
SgTiC/2%CNT-CDC	276	1510	0.38	2.94

Table II. Integral specific capacitance values calculated from cyclic voltammetry data (ΔE from 0 V to 3.2 V; $\nu = 10 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$; $\nu = 100 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$; $\nu = 500 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$), capacitance values calculated from impedance spectroscopy measurements (in EtMeImBF₄ $\Delta E = 3.2 \text{ V}$; in Et₃MeNBF₄+AN $\Delta E = 3.0 \text{ V}$; $f = 1 \text{ mHz}$) and time constant values for the electrode materials in different electrolytes applied.

Electrolyte	Integral capacitance (F g^{-1}) from CV data			Capacitance (F g^{-1}) from impedance spectroscopy	Time constant τ (s)
	10 mV s^{-1}	100 mV s^{-1}	500 mV s^{-1}		
EtMeImBF ₄					
SgTiC-CDC	122	116	96	155	0.80
SgTiC/1%CNT-CDC	115	109	94	147	0.86
SgTiC/2%CNT-CDC	103	96	80	132	0.85
Et ₃ MeNBF ₄ + AN					
SgTiC-CDC	112	111	106	139	0.15
SgTiC/1%CNT-CDC	104	103	100	130	0.14
SgTiC/2%CNT-CDC	93	92	89	117	0.14

Table III. Capacitance (C_{CC}), energy efficiency (η_{en}) and coulombic efficiency (η_{coul}) values calculated from constant current measurements (in EtMeImBF₄ $\Delta E = 3.2$ V; in Et₃MeNBF₄+AN $\Delta E = 3.0$ V; $j = 1$ A g⁻¹ and $j = 10$ A g⁻¹).

Electrolyte	1 A g ⁻¹			10 A g ⁻¹		
	C_{CC} (F g ⁻¹)	η_{en} (%)	η_{coul} (%)	C_{CC} (F g ⁻¹)	η_{en} (%)	η_{coul} (%)
EtMeImBF ₄						
SgTiC-CDC	123	95.10	99.99	112	83.08	99.58
SgTiC/1%CNT-CDC	117	94.24	99.98	106	81.07	99.56
SgTiC/2%CNT-CDC	102	93.51	99.90	92	80.04	99.07
Et ₃ MeNBF ₄ + AN						
SgTiC-CDC	111	97.56	99.38	—	—	—
SgTiC/1%CNT-CDC	103	97.75	99.96	—	—	—
SgTiC/2%CNT-CDC	90	95.59	99.26	—	—	—

where j is the current density, dt is the change in time and ΔE is the cell potential.

The CC/CD curves (Fig. 5) for the synthesized materials are nearly linear and symmetrical at all current densities applied (1–10 A g⁻¹), showing very good electrochemical reversibility, energetic and coulombic efficiencies (Table III). The nearly linear shape of CC/CD curves at different current densities (1 A g⁻¹ and 10 A g⁻¹) demonstrates that there is no significant contribution of the faradaic reactions inside of the micro-mesoporous carbon electrode structure. Very slightly different capacitance values obtained by CC/CD method at discharge current density 10 A g⁻¹ from CV method at $v = 10$ mV s⁻¹ data (Table III) can be explained by physical differences in methods applied for charging/discharging of the electrodes and by the fact that at 10 A g⁻¹ the adsorption/desorption equilibrium has not been established.

The cycling efficiency, i.e. the so-called coulombic efficiency (η_{coul}) (Table III) has been calculated as a ratio of charge densities released and accumulated ($Q_{discharge}/Q_{charge}$) during the discharging and charging steps of the EDLCs. The calculated η_{coul} values for all materials exceeded 99%. The IR-drop values are very low at current density 1 A g⁻¹. Only very small IR-drop (from 0.05 V to 0.10 V) can be seen for EDLCs at 10 A g⁻¹ discharging current.

For more correct energy accumulation analysis, the CC/CD curves were integrated and the energy densities stored (E_{in}) and released (E_{out}) were obtained based on Eq. 4:

$$E_{in,out} = j \int_{t(\Delta E_{min})}^{t(\Delta E_{max})} \Delta E(t) dt. \quad [4]$$

The values of energy efficiency (ratio of energy released and accumulated), where t is time in seconds and ΔE_{max} and ΔE_{min} are maximal and minimal cell potentials applied^{47,60} have been calculated based on

Eq. 5:

$$\eta_{en} = \frac{E_{out}}{E_{in}} \cdot 100\%, \quad [5]$$

The calculated energy efficiency values, η_{en} , vary from 93 to 95% (at 1 A g⁻¹), and charge (coulombic) efficiency values (above 99%) show that sol-gel titanium carbide derived carbon materials combined with EtMeImBF₄ and Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN (η_{en} from 97.6 to 95.6%) as an electrolyte, respectively, are nearly ideal components for various energy/power storage, i.e. EDLC applications.

Impedance spectroscopy data and complex power calculations.— Nyquist ($-Z''$, Z') plots (Figs. 6a and 7a) were measured in ac frequency range from 1 mHz to 300 kHz at fixed cell potentials from 0 to 3.8 V (EtMeImBF₄) or 0 to 3.6 V (Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN). The shape of the Nyquist plots in Figs. 6a and 7a show that there is no noticeable deviation from ideal polarizability conditions for EtMeImBF₄ up to 3.6 V and for Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN up to 3.2 V. The shape of the Nyquist plots is independent of ΔE applied, if $\Delta E < 3.4$ V for EtMeImBF₄ and $\Delta E < 3.2$ V for Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN based EDLCs, indicating that there are no quick faradaic processes at or inside of the SgTiC-CDC electrodes. There is no semicircle at higher ac frequencies ($f \geq 100$ Hz), indicating that the charge storage steps are very quick inside the synthesized carbon electrodes and the series resistance of a material, charge transfer resistance inside the micro-mesoporous carbon structure and the mass transfer resistance (R_{CE}) are very low and practically independent of ΔE applied if $\Delta E \leq 3.2$ V.^{61,62}

Thus, the Nyquist plots for SgTiC-CDC EDLCs studied consist mainly of two parts. First, the so-called “porous” region with a slope of a nearly -45° in ac frequency region $0.1 < f < 100$ Hz, characteristic of the mass transfer limited process with adsorption boundary conditions in the micro-mesoporous carbon electrode matrix of an electrode.^{47,61} Second, within the low-frequency ac region, so-called double-layer capacitance region (finite length region) with a slope of a -90° that indicates the adsorption step rate limited process inside the

Figure 5. Constant current charge/discharge data at current density (a) $j = 1$ A g⁻¹ and (b) $j = 10$ A g⁻¹ for the EDLCs completed using SgTiC-CDC, SgTiC/1%CNT-CDC and SgTiC/2%CNT-CDC, noted in Figure.

Figure 6. (a) Impedance complex plane plots, (b) phase angle, θ , vs. ac frequency dependencies, (c) specific series capacitance, C_s , vs. ac frequency dependencies, (d) normalized reactive power $|Q|/|S|$ and active power $|P|/|S|$ vs. ac frequency plots, (e) $\log|-Z''|$ vs. $\log f$ plots and (f) specific parallel capacitance and specific series capacitance vs. $\log f$ dependencies at cell potential $\Delta E = 3.2$ V for the EDLCs completed using electrodes and electrolytes noted in Figure.

Figure 7. (a) Impedance complex plane plots, (b) phase angle, θ , vs. ac frequency dependencies, (c) specific series capacitance, C_s , vs. ac frequency dependencies, (d) ratio of parallel capacitance and series capacitance C_p/C_s vs. frequency dependencies at different cell potentials (noted in Figure) for EDLCs completed with SgTiC-CDC electrodes in EtMeImBF₄ and Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN electrolytes (noted in Figure).

porous electrodes.^{47,53,54,61} SgTiC-CDC without CNT addition has the highest value of “knee” frequency (0.38 Hz), which indicates easier accessibility of electrolyte ions into the pores and better performance at fast charge and discharge conditions.^{46,63} Comparison of the data for two electrolytes shows that the series resistance value depends noticeably on the electrolyte used, increasing from non-aqueous Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN to EtMeImBF₄. The so-called “porous region” length in Nyquist plot with slope -45° (at $f \leq 0.1$ Hz), obtaining the mass transfer resistance value ($R_{\text{pore}} \leq 0.5$ and $2.5 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, respectively), is very short (3.5–4.0 times shorter) for AN based electrolyte, explained by the higher conductivity of Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN electrolyte.

The phase angle, θ , vs. ac frequency dependencies are shown in Fig. 6b. For all synthesized materials, the phase angle θ was nearly -90° (at $f \leq 0.1$ Hz), demonstrating nearly ideal capacitive behavior.^{47,60–62} However, there is very strong dependency of characteristic frequency on electrode electrolyte (where $\theta = -45^\circ$), indicating that the time constant for Et₃MeImBF₄ + AN based EDLC is noticeably shorter than that for EtMeImBF₄ based EDLC.

The values of series capacitance have been calculated according to Eq. 6:^{6,47,61,62}

$$C_s(\omega) = \frac{-1}{\omega Z''(\omega)} \quad [6]$$

and are given in Fig. 6c ($\omega = 2\pi f$ is an angular frequency). The C_s vs. $\log f$ plots have long plateaus at $f < 1$ Hz and the highest capacitance value of 155 F g^{-1} (at 3.2 V) has been established for SgTiC-CDC. For Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN based EDLCs the C_s values are somewhat lower (140 F g^{-1}) than those for RTIL based EDLC, explained by larger molar volume of Et₃MeN⁺ than that for EtMeIm⁺ or lower surface concentration of cation Et₃MeN⁺ compared with EtMeIm⁺ at micro-mesoporous electrode surface.

For more detailed analysis, the values of complex power were calculated^{19,47} and the dependence of the normalized real part ($|P|/|S|$) and imaginary part ($|Q|/|S|$) of the complex power on ac frequency are presented in Fig. 6d. Characteristic charging/discharging time constant τ values, given in Fig. 6d and Table III, have been calculated from the frequency of interception points f_{int} of the $|P|/|S|$ and $|Q|/|S|$ curves.^{6,46,64,65} The τ_R value obtained for SgTiC-CDC|EtMeImBF₄ system ($\tau_R = 0.80$ s) is substantially shorter if compared with τ_R obtained for activated sucrose derived carbon ($\tau_R = 20$ s),⁶⁶ carbon cloth ($\tau_R = 8$ s)⁶⁷ and even slightly shorter compared with carbon material synthesized from commercially available TiC ($\tau_R = 1.76$ s)¹⁷ and D-glucose derived carbon ($\tau_R = 1.1$ s)⁴⁶ systems in EtMeImBF₄. Somewhat shorter τ_R values ($\tau_R = 0.14$ s and 0.15 s) have been calculated for SgTiC-CDC|Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN system and for microporous TiC-CDC|Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN system ($\tau_R = 0.54$ s).⁶⁸ Extremely short characteristic time constants and high capacitance values indicate that synthesized materials can be used for completing of very high power density EDLCs.

Two linear regions have been observed in $\log|-Z'|$, $\log f$ plots^{47,60–62,69} given in Fig. 6e: first from 100 to 0.5 Hz (so-called micro-mesoporous region) with -0.476 slope, i.e. nearly equal to that for ideal semi-infinite mass transfer process (slope -0.5), and the second linear region (slope -0.978) at lower frequencies (from $f < 0.5$ Hz), which is characteristic of the ideal adsorption step limited processes (slope -1.0) in EDLCs. For Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN the less expressed deviation from ideal -0.5 slope⁶² can be explained by more ideal behavior of the electrolyte in comparison with RTIL.

Overlapping of the parallel capacitance, C_p , vs. $\log f$ and C_s vs. $\log f$ plots (Fig. 6f), where C_p is calculated according to Eq. 7:

$$C_p(\omega) = C_s(\omega) \left[1 + \tan^2 \left(\frac{-Z'(\omega)}{Z''(\omega)} \right) \right], \quad [7]$$

shows that equilibrium capacitance values have been established and the systems under study are ideally polarizable up to 3.2 V^{47,61,62}. However, noticeable deviation toward faradaic charge transfer process has been established only at $\Delta E \geq 3.8$ V. For Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN based

EDLC, deviation toward faradaic processes can be observed at $\Delta E \geq 3.4$ V.

The shape of the Nyquist plots in Fig. 7a for EDLC completed using Sg-TiC-CDC material (without CNT addition) shows that noticeable deviation from ideal polarizability has been observed only at $\Delta E \geq 3.6$ V. The phase angle, θ , vs. ac frequency dependencies (Fig. 7b) are in an agreement with Nyquist plot data. Thus, the noticeable deviation from ideal polarizability starts at $\Delta E \geq 3.6$ V, when the absolute (θ) values start to decrease ($|\theta| \leq 90^\circ$). The series capacitance C_s vs. $\log f$ plots (Fig. 7c) have long plateaus at $f < 1$ Hz and C_s increases with the cell potential applied, explained by the increase of Gibbs adsorption of ions at higher positive and negative surface charge densities⁷⁰ or by the inaccurate equivalent circuit model applied, which was a series RC circuit for calculation of C_s and C_p values from Nyquist plots.

Ragone plots.—The experimentally measured gravimetric and volumetric Ragone plots (specific energy, E , vs. specific power, P , dependencies) calculated to the total material weight of two electrodes (for the EDLCs based on different synthesized electrodes) have been obtained from the constant power tests within the cell potential range from 3.2 V to 1.6 V for EtMeImBF₄ and Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN based EDLCs^{6,67} and are shown in Figs. 8a–8b. The Ragone plots show that high energy and very high power densities ($\sim 100 \text{ kW kg}^{-1}$ at 10 Wh kg^{-1}) have been achieved. Somewhat lower energy densities have been calculated for Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN based EDLCs at moderate power values. However, quicker decrease of E has been calculated for EtMeImBF₄ based EDLC due to higher series resistance values caused by lower conductivity of the electrolyte. Data in Fig. 8b show that good volumetric energy densities at $P = 10 \text{ kW dm}^{-3}$, $E = 7 \text{ Wh dm}^{-3}$ have been achieved. The EDLCs completed show weak influence of the CNT addition into the precursor carbide on the stored specific energy and power values delivered in EDLCs completed using sol-gel synthesized carbon electrodes.

In Fig. 8c comparison of Ragone plots with other EDLCs containing EtMeImBF₄ as an electrolyte are given. Data in Fig. 8c show that for SgTiC-CDC based EDLCs higher energy density values are established at higher power densities, compared to microporous carbon derived from commercially available TiC,⁴⁷ D-glucose derived carbon (GDAC-12h),⁴⁶ micro-mesoporous D-glucose derived carbon (MMP GDAC),⁴⁸ steam activated carbon derived from SiC⁴⁷ and carbon derived from granulated white sugar (GWS carbon).¹⁸ Thus, for higher power densities, more mesoporous material is urgently needed.

Conclusions

The energy-related properties of the EDLCs based on room temperature ionic liquid (1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate, EtMeImBF₄) and Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN and on the electrode materials synthesized from sol-gel titanium carbide derived carbon (SgTiC-CDC) were investigated using the cyclic voltammetry, galvanostatic charge/discharge, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and constant power discharge methods.

Cyclic voltammetry data show that completed EDLCs demonstrate practically ideal capacitive behavior at cell potential up to $\Delta E \leq 3.6$ V and potential scan rate up to $v \leq 500 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$. Very high C_s value of 176 F g^{-1} at $\Delta E = 3.6 \text{ V}$ (155 F g^{-1} at $\Delta E = 3.2 \text{ V}$) for EtMeImBF₄ system has been established. Cyclic voltammetry, impedance and constant current data indicate that even at very high potential scan rates ($v \leq 500 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$), there is no significant potential drop in the porous CDC matrix. This is probably caused by the extra developed mesoporosity, because the sol-gel synthesis provides additional amount of mesopores in the carbon powders within the range from 4 to 10 nm. The highest specific capacitance value (impedance data) $C = 176 \text{ F g}^{-1}$ (EtMeImBF₄, $\Delta E = 3.6 \text{ V}$, $f = 1 \text{ mHz}$) and $C = 145 \text{ F g}^{-1}$ (Et₃MeNBF₄ + AN, $\Delta E = 3.0 \text{ V}$, $f = 1 \text{ mHz}$) has been obtained for the carbon material without CNT addition. Only weakly lower capacitance values have been observed if compared with materials that have CNT addition in raw paste. Phase angle values above

Figure 8. (a) Gravimetric and (b) volumetric Ragone plots measured within cell potential range 3.2 V to 1.6 V for the EDLCs completed using SgTiC-CDC, SgTiC/1%CNT-CDC and SgTiC/2%CNT-CDC as electrodes (noted in Figure) and (c) gravimetric Ragone plots for different carbon materials (noted in Figure) measured within cell potential range 3.0 V to 1.5 V in various ionic liquids and $\text{Et}_3\text{MeNBF}_4 + \text{AN}$.

-85° for all materials (at low frequencies) indicate that a nearly ideally polarizable EDLCs have been completed and tested.

The calculated energy efficiency values for all synthesized carbon based EDLC systems vary within the range from 93% to 97% (at 1 A g^{-1}), while the calculated coulombic efficiency values exceeded 99%, showing that EDLCs completed with synthesized hierarchical micro-mesoporous carbon materials in 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate and in $\text{Et}_3\text{MeNBF}_4 + \text{acetonitrile}$ as an electrolyte are suitable for very high energy and power density applications. The weakly lower electrochemical capacitance and energy density of EDLCs containing CNT can be explained by the lower specific surface area values compared with SgTiC-CDC without CNT additions. Noticeably higher energy densities at moderate power density (5 kW kg^{-1}) have been calculated for viscous EtMeImBF_4 based EDLC. It should be stressed that very high power densities ($> 100 \text{ kW kg}^{-1}$) at high energy density (30 Wh kg^{-1}) have been achieved for $\text{Et}_3\text{MeNBF}_4 + \text{AN}$ based EDLCs. For EtMeImBF_4 based EDLC somewhat lower energy density 10 Wh kg^{-1} at 100 kW kg^{-1} power density has been established. Thus, in addition to optimized mesoporosity of the electrode material, the electrolyte viscosity should be reduced and conductivity should be increased for very high energy density devices at extremely high power densities.

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